

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on phase 2 hackathon, including climate change impacts on renewable energy production
Deliverable number	D28 (Del. Rel. No. D5.4)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	30/06/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MISU
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This report describes the outcome of the Phase 2 hackathon, building on the implemented online diagnostics for renewable energy from the development phase, and using available production runs to evaluate impacts of changing weather conditions related to climate change, on energy production.

Work package in charge:

WP5

Lead author:

Frida Bender

Other contributing authors:

Thorsten Mauritsen, Dragana Bojović

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Dragana Bojović

2nd reviewer: Eulàlia Baulenas Serra

Contacts: frida.bender@misu.su.se, thorsten.mauritsen@misu.su.se

Visit us on: www.nextgems-h2020.eu

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the authors view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Executive summary

The sixth nextGEMS Hackathon was hosted by the Storms & Radiation theme, at the Swedish museum of natural history in Stockholm. Over 70 project members from all themes, and invited guests from three European renewable energy companies, came together for four days of analysis of the latest simulations with the two storm-resolving models, sharing and reflection on results from the project that is now coming to an end, and looking towards continued future developments and collaborations.

Contents

Executive summary	3
Objectives and Synergies	5
1 Hackathon report	8
1.1 Hackathon components	8
1.1.1 Pre-hackathon training	9
1.1.2 Opening discussion	9
1.1.3 Group work	9
1.1.4 Networking and science exchange	9
1.1.5 Science communication	10
1.1.6 Closing discussion	10
1.2 Knowledge co-production: climate change impacts on renewable energy production	10
1.3 Data-handling	12
1.4 General reflection	12
2 Conclusion	13

Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP5	Relevance in this deliverable?
To test hypotheses, and quantify processes related to aerosols, clouds and their influences on climate change with a new degree of precision and fidelity. (O1 and O2)	no
To develop parametrisations of cloud micro-physics and mixing, and apply advanced data-assimilation methods to model tuning. (O1)	no
To advance science and support efforts to operationalise the Paris agreement to limit global warming, through improved assessments of aerosol forcing, radiative feedbacks and climate sensitivity. (O2)	no
To exploit the online diagnostics implemented in the Development phase to investigate the impact of a changing climate on solar and wind energy production in a joint hackathon. (O3)	yes

1 Hackathon report

Storms & Radiation hosted the sixth and final hackathon in the nextGEMS project, that took place in Stockholm, Sweden, on March 25-March 28. The meeting was referred to as "The final countdown" and focus was on summarizing key findings from the project, addressing remaining questions, as well as looking forward and discussing the legacy of nextGEMS. It also included a strong component of stake-holder involvement with invited guests from the renewable energy sector, who worked on challenge problems with the project members. All together, 73 participants from 12 countries, gathered for a few days of intense hacking, collaboration and community building.

Figure 1: Group photo of hackathon participants outside the Swedish museum of natural history. Photo by T. Vostry, Latest Thinking.

We report here on the components of the hackathon, and add a general reflection on the role the hackathons played for the project.

1.1 Hackathon components

The venue was the Swedish museum of natural history, located just off the Stockholm University main campus. A video documentation was made, and can be found in the nextGEMS media library.

1.1.1 Pre-hackathon training

This far into the project, the data access and analysis introductions were done online prior to the hackathon. All hackathon participants were directed to recorded explanatory presentations, and invited to online Q&A sessions, to ensure that everyone had accounts, access to data, and tools for analysis. There was also a pre-hackathon plot challenge, where everyone could produce and submit a plot prior to the meeting. A prize was given to the winning contribution at the end of the hackathon.

1.1.2 Opening discussion

For the introductory session on Wednesday afternoon, each of the themes presented some highlights from their respective work packages, emphasizing not least with visualizations the new insights and level of detail that the high resolution simulations can offer. There were also presentations from the ICON and IFS development teams, on the latest updates on the simulations available to work with.

1.1.3 Group work

The main activity of the event was hacking. The work was organised in the themes such that Storms & Radiation, Storms & Ocean, and Storms & Land worked in separate rooms, with common access to the data support team. In addition there was a dedicated Renewable Energy team, with participants from three different energy stake-holders: Vestas, Statkraft, and Anemos.

Group work addressed topics such as e.g. extreme precipitation, convective organisation, aerosol forcing, clouds and cloud feedbacks (Storms & Radiation), tropical climate variability and teleconnections, tropical cyclones, eastern boundary upwelling and marine ecosystem implications (Storms & Ocean), atmospheric blockings, heat waves and dry spells, surface radiation balance and solar energy potential (Storms & Land). The Renewable energy group worked on the broad question of how wind, and thereby wind energy production, will change in the coming decades. In parallel Storms & Society continued stakeholder engagement, dissemination and communication efforts, as well as work on storylines and social network analysis.

The Thursday, which was the second and final day of actual hacking started with a scrum, where each of the groups presented a single plot highlighting their work so far. After a vote and prize ceremony, the hacking continued for all.

1.1.4 Networking and science exchange

On the first evening an ice breaker was held at the Department of Meteorology at Stockholm University. This also entailed a micro poster session: all participants were encouraged to bring a single plot to illustrate their nextGEMS work, that they carried as they mingled, and this spurred discussion throughout the evening.

The second day ended with a key note presentation by professor Gabriele Messori, from the department of Earth Sciences at Uppsala University, on "Data-driven forecasts of extreme events and impact forecasting". This topic inspired a lively discussion on AI vs physical model forecasting, that continued at the hackathon dinner.

The early career scientists got together for dinner also on the evening of the third day, and during all days everyone had joint lunches and coffee breaks with plenty of time for networking across research themes, institutions, and career stages. The Storms & Society theme invited everyone to fill out a survey about the self-perceived impact of nextGEMS hackathons, and also shared their results from ongoing social network analysis.

1.1.5 Science communication

In addition to the general hackathon video, Latest Thinking produced film material where each of the themes commented on their progress throughout the project, what insights they have gained from the work with the nextGEMS SR-ESMs, and how they had met the goals defined in the very first videos. This material will be available in the online nextGEMS media library.

1.1.6 Closing discussion

In the closing plenary session, each of the groups presented summaries of their findings during the hackathon. NextGEMS PI professor Bjorn Stevens also gave a summarizing presentation, highlighting the efforts and accomplishments in the project, and pointing towards the future, ways to continue working with the existing data, work with the models to produce new simulations and experiments, and not least participate in the up-coming global hackathon, that is largely driven by the nextGEMS working model.

1.2 Knowledge co-production: climate change impacts on renewable energy production

This last NextGEMS hackathon again had renewable energy as a theme. The meeting was well visited with 4 researchers from three different companies, Vestas, Anemos and Statkraft, that joined the hackathon in person. Several NextGEMS scientists were also assigned to the renewable energy group.

This time we decided to focus on how climate change would impact different aspects of renewable energy production. At the beginning of the NextGEMS project, when we had the first renewable energy hackathon, the participating companies at that time, Vestas and Iberdrola, explained how they would typically assume that climate change is not affecting the conditions under which they work. They would simply determine the climatology of conditions for a site and assume that will stay the same over the life time of a given project (about 30 years). This attitude towards climate change has completely changed over the last few years where the industry now considers climate change as an important factor to consider over the typical lifetime

Figure 2: Change in the number of days with strong surface wind speeds in winter (December, January and February, DJF) between the AMIP and the AMIP+4K experiments.

of installations.

Of particular interest to stakeholders were extreme winds, icing risk and turbulence. All factors are related to durability and safety around the installations. For this purpose, both the NextGEMS future scenario coupled simulations, as well as the more idealised atmosphere-only AMIP and AMIP+4K experiments wherein the effects of a uniform 4 degree global warming can be explored, were utilized. As an example, it was found that extreme wind speeds in winter increased over Europe, exemplified here by the number of high wind speed days (Figure 2), although the same was found also for extreme wind speed strength. The European region really stands out, in an otherwise decreasing number of days and extremes. Also explored was the risk of icing, done using the surface dew point depression, finding a drying over most land regions but more neutral results at high latitudes where icing is most common. Finally, the risk of strong turbulence and wind shear was explored using the lower boundary layer static stability, finding a reduction in stability over most land regions.

The following key messages summarize the individual interviews with the four stakeholders from the energy sector, conducted by the project social scientists during the hackathon:

1. Data Use: Renewable energy frequently runs into the issue of public meteorological data lacking the vertical resolution the industry requires. There is hence increasing reliance on commercial data providers for risk assessments and asset-level forecasts. The participants were familiar with the CMIP data, which usually arrive via consultancy reports.

2. Climate Questions: Participants confirmed their interest in future conditions for wind, solar, and drought risk (for hydropower). They were not too worried about having precise quantitative results. Rather, even directional indications, e.g., increase/decrease of temperature or wind, were seen as useful. Stakeholders face organizational pressure to make informed projections, even when uncertainty remains high.

3. Collaboration Between Research and Industry: Participants emphasized the importance of industry–research dialogue to ensure relevant parameters are prioritized in expensive climate simulations. Some were also engaged in research projects, particularly with academics seeking practical applications. They felt that the current collaboration was functional but could be improved—important to know what industry values to inform model outputs. Finally, for some stakeholders, involvement in nextGEMS through the hackathon was seen as a learning opportunity, particularly in terms of data handling and processing. As one interviewee summarized: “[this collaboration is useful to learn] how to use data and what to use it for; how to untangle the data storage and how to unpack data; and finally how the data is made.”

All in all, as NextGEMS scientists we were surprised by the evolving stakeholder interest in climate change and various risks and impacts, much more diversified than purely renewable energy production potential. The ability of the stakeholder researchers to directly engage with the data speaks not only to the well prepared data, tools and instructions provided by NextGEMS, but also the capacity in the stakeholder community experts to leverage such large datasets now and in future projects such as Destination Earth.

1.3 Data-handling

The easy.gems website, collecting scripts to facilitate data analysis continues to grow, and constitutes an important resource for newcomers as well as more experienced project members and hackathon participants.

1.4 General reflection

The hackathon concept, introduced as a key component of the nextGEMS project, has been successful. The common focus on hacking during the meetings has not only been productive, but also contributed to team-building and exchange of knowledge, ideas and results in ways that regular meetings often struggle more to do. Rather than focus on presenting, the focus is on producing, and finding solutions to common problems. The set-up gives everyone, at all career stages, a chance to get directly involved in the data handling, and there is ample opportunity for early career researchers to take leading roles in hacking sub groups, and push towards their own and the project goals. Although ongoing analysis of structured surveys on the hackathons will provide more detail and well-founded conclusions, the mere fact that the sixth hackathon attracted more than 70 participants speaks to the fact that they are an appreciated way to meet within the project. We anticipate that they will be missed, and that future projects will use the nextGEMS setup as inspiration.

2 Conclusion

The sixth and final nextGEMS hackathon, was held in Stockholm. In addition to group work in the themes Storms & Radiation, Storms & Land, and Storms & Ocean, addressing questions ranging from climate feedbacks and aerosol forcing to extreme events, tropical climate variability and air-sea exchange, we involved renewable energy stakeholders in challenge problems relating to changes in wind energy production conditions with climate change. Of particular interest to stakeholders was extremes winds and icing risk. Summarizing communication videos were produced and subsequently published online, and social network analysis performed by Storms & Society. This hackathon, as the previous ones, offered valuable opportunities for scientific exchange, collaboration and community building